

Enhancing IIoT Security: BERT-Driven Intrusion Detection with MLP in Industrial Networks

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Abstract—Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are pivotal in securing Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) networks, where the convergence of operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT) has heightened vulnerability to sophisticated cyber threats. The complexity, scale, and heterogeneity of IIoT environments necessitate advanced threat detection mechanisms capable of identifying and mitigating attacks in real-time. In this study, we propose a novel deep learning-based IDS framework that integrates Google BERT for advanced feature extraction and a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) for robust classification. Our methodology is evaluated using three IIoT-specific benchmark datasets: CIC APT IIoT 2024, WUSTL IIoT 2021, and WUSTL IIoT 2018, which encompass diverse attack scenarios and network behaviors. To address the prevalent issue of class imbalance in these datasets, we employ the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE), enhancing the model's ability to learn and generalize minority attack patterns effectively. Experimental results demonstrate that our proposed framework significantly improves the detection accuracy of cyber threats in IIoT environments. The system's scalability, efficiency, and real-time applicability make it a promising solution for safeguarding OT networks against evolving cyber threats. This study provides a practical and high-performance approach to enhancing the resilience of IIoT ecosystems.

Index Terms—Intrusion Detection System (IDS), Industrial IoT, Operations Technology, Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT), Cybersecurity, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Imbalanced Dataset.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE rapid adoption of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) technologies has revolutionized operational technology (OT) environments, enabling real-time monitoring, automation, and data-driven decision-making. However, this increased connectivity has exposed IIoT systems to sophisticated cyber threats [1], making them

prime targets for malicious actors. Unlike traditional IT networks, OT systems oversee critical industrial operations, where security breaches can result in severe disruptions, financial losses, and safety hazards. Consequently, Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) have become crucial for proactively detecting and mitigating cyber threats in IIoT environments [2].

Traditional IDS solutions primarily rely on rule-based or signature-based techniques, which often fail to detect emerging threats, including zero-day attacks [3]. Although traditional Machine Learning (ML) approaches offer improvements, they require extensive feature engineering, domain expertise, and struggle with the high dimensionality and dynamic nature of IIoT traffic. They also face limitations in handling imbalanced datasets typical in cybersecurity scenarios, leading to performance degradation against minority-class attacks.

Several recent works have proposed ML-based solutions to address these challenges. Bushnag et al. [4] introduced a two-level ML-based IDS using Random Forest, achieving high accuracy but highlighting limitations in speed and adaptability. Mao et al. [5] developed a federated incremental learning IDS, focusing on data privacy and continuous learning, yet resource optimization remains challenging. Arsalan et al. [6] presented a lightweight CNN achieving high accuracy, but its performance under evolving attacks was untested. Similarly, Kumar et al. [7] deployed ML models at the fog layer, attaining impressive accuracy on standard datasets but were limited by reliance on traditional feature extraction methods.

While transfer learning (TL) techniques [8] and hybrid DL/ML strategies [9], [10] have improved detection accuracy, they still fail to fully exploit the rich contextual relationships inherent in IIoT traffic data. Despite their advantages, TL and ML-based intrusion

detection methods in IIoT environments face several challenges. One major limitation of TL techniques is their struggle with domain adaptation, especially in highly dynamic and heterogeneous IIoT networks. These models often require extensive fine-tuning to generalize effectively across varying network conditions, making them less adaptable to real-world deployments. Similarly, hybrid ML/DL approaches, while enhancing detection capabilities, often fall short in capturing complex contextual dependencies within network traffic. Many of these models still rely on handcrafted feature engineering or traditional statistical methods, which may not be sufficient for identifying subtle and evolving attack patterns.

Motivated by these challenges, our work proposes a novel DL-based IDS framework that integrates Google BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) for advanced meaningful context-aware feature extraction directly from raw, unstructured data with a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier for intrusion classification tailored specifically for IIoT environments, ultimately improving detection accuracy and adaptability in evolving cyber threat landscapes. Moreover, our proposed solution integrates the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) to address class imbalance, significantly improving detection performance against minority attack classes. We provide a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed approach using three benchmark datasets (CIC-APT-IIoT-2024, WUSTL-IIoT-2021, WUSTL-IIoT-2018), covering diverse attack scenarios related to the IIoT network conditions. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed IDS performance is excellent for all benchmark datasets, overcoming the limitations of state-of-the-art classifiers applied to IIoT networks.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider the reference architecture depicted in Figure 1, specifically tailored for intrusion detection within IIoT environments. This architecture comprises interconnected industrial components such as sensors, valves, pumps, motors, and Remote Terminal Units (RTUs), which communicate with Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs), microcontrollers, and Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems. Communication occurs over a combination of Industrial Ethernet and fieldbus technologies (e.g., Profibus, Profinet) with the associated gateways.

The Intrusion Detection System (IDS) plays a critical role in securing the industrial network infrastructure.

Positioned strategically between the IIoT network and external connections, the IDS continuously monitors network traffic to detect and classify potential cyber threats. To facilitate detailed traffic monitoring, dedicated network probes may be placed at multiple strategic locations and various hierarchical levels within the OT domain. These probes sniff traffic within their respective segments and forward the captured data through an Ethernet connection to the IDS for further analysis.

Attackers may attempt to infiltrate the IIoT infrastructure from several points. External attackers can exploit vulnerabilities by accessing the network remotely via the internet, bypassing conventional firewall protections. Internally, attackers may directly compromise local components such as sensors, RTUs, PLCs, or field gateways, exploiting weaknesses in the operational network.

III. PROPOSED INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM

The IDS training involves several structured phases, building on state-of-the-art machine learning techniques to achieve high accuracy in threat detection. Initially, as shown in Figure 1, raw network traffic data collected from the IIoT environment undergoes a rigorous preprocessing pipeline. This pipeline includes duplication removal to ensure data integrity, label mapping to standardize classification tasks, and addressing class imbalance issues using the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE). Such preprocessing results in balanced and representative datasets, significantly improving the classifier's training quality and generalization capability.

Following data preprocessing, our system employs Google BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) to perform advanced feature extraction [11]. Specifically, raw numerical network features from the datasets are first tokenized and transformed into textual representations compatible with BERT's input requirements. These tokenized inputs pass through BERT's transformer architecture, where multiple self-attention layers effectively capture complex contextual relationships and hidden dependencies inherent in IIoT network traffic. This step produces high-dimensional embeddings rich in meaningful patterns, significantly surpassing traditional feature extraction methods that typically require domain-specific, manual feature engineering. Finally, the embeddings generated by BERT feed into a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier.

Fig. 1. Proposed System Model

The MLP consists of a single hidden layer containing 256 neurons activated by a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), introducing non-linear capabilities necessary for capturing intricate traffic patterns. The classifier employs an adaptive learning rate strategy, dynamically adjusting its step sizes during backpropagation to enhance training efficiency. Training proceeds over a maximum of 200 iterations to ensure robust learning of distinct patterns between normal and attack scenarios.

IV. VALIDATION SETUP

To validate the effectiveness and applicability of the proposed IDS described in the previous section, we conducted extensive experiments utilizing three diverse and representative IIoT benchmark datasets: CIC-APT-IIoT-2024 [12], WUSTL-IIoT-2021 [13], and WUSTL-IIoT-SCADA-2018 [14]. These datasets, as detailed in Table I, cover a wide range of realistic IIoT network traffic patterns, including normal operational behaviors and sophisticated cyber threats. Specifically, CIC-APT-IIoT-2024 comprises advanced persistent threats (APT) scenarios captured within a realistic IIoT infrastructure, whereas WUSTL-IIoT-2021 and WUSTL-IIoT-2018 datasets provide real-world traffic collected from SCADA and IIoT networks, encompassing various types of cyberattack strategies and operational conditions. The inclusion of these datasets ensures a comprehensive evaluation of our IDS model's performance, demonstrating its robustness and generalizability across diverse IIoT network environments.

A. Performance Metrics

The proposed approach was thoroughly evaluated using five distinct metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and the Confusion Matrix. In evaluating the performance of a classification model, the True Positive (TP) refers to instances where the model correctly identifies actual positive cases, while the True Negative (TN) denotes cases where the model accurately classifies negative instances. False Positive (FP) occurs when the model mistakenly labels a negative instance as positive, and False Negative (FN) describes situations where the model fails to detect a positive case, incorrectly classifying it as negative.

1) *Accuracy*: Accuracy $\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$ measures the overall effectiveness of the classifier. It is defined as the ratio of correctly predicted instances to the total number of predictions, providing a general indication of model performance.

2) *Precision*: Precision $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ measures the accuracy of positive predictions. It is defined as the proportion of true positive instances among all instances predicted as positive, reflecting the model's ability to minimize false positives.

3) *Recall*: Recall $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$ measures the model's ability to identify actual positive instances. It is defined as the proportion of true positives among all actual positives, highlighting the model's sensitivity.

4) *F1-Score*: The F1-Score $(2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}})$ provides a balanced evaluation by combining precision and recall. It is defined as their harmonic mean and is

TABLE I
DATASET IDENTIFICATION

Dataset	No	Labels	Records	SMOTE	Other Information	
				*: Oversampling **: Undersampling		
CIC-APT-IIoT-2024	1	Normal	21,598,215	500,000 **	No. of Features	70
	2	Collection	460	2,500 *	Dataset Size	09.14 GB
	3	Cleanup	192	2,000 *	Attack Category	Advanced Persistent Threats
	4	Discovery	138	1,500 *	Total Records	21,599,219
	5	Credential Access	58	1,000 *	Attack Records	1,004
	6	Command and Control	56	1,000 *		
	7	Persistence	44	1,500 *		
	8	Exfiltration	42	1,500 *		
	9	Lateral Movement	14	1,000 *		
WUSTL-IIoT-2021	1	Normal	1,107,448	500,000 **	No. of Features	41
	2	Command Injection	259	1,500 *	Dataset Size	390.80 MB
	3	DoS	78,305	100,000 *	Total Records	1,194,464
	4	Reconnaissance	8,240	15,000 *	Attack Records	87,016
	5	Backdoor	212	1,500 *		
WUSTL-IIoT-2018 ICS SCADA	1	Normal	6,634,581	-	No. of Features	7
	2	Attack	403,402	-	Dataset Size	189.90 MB
					Duplicate Records	6,975,024
					Total No. of Records	7,037,983

particularly effective for assessing model performance on imbalanced datasets.

5) *Confusion Matrix*: A confusion matrix is a performance evaluation tool for classification models that outlines how many predictions fall into four categories: TP, TN, FP, and FN. It provides a clear snapshot of the model’s ability to correctly distinguish between different classes.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results in Table II demonstrate the effectiveness of the approach across various classes of attacks and normal traffic. For the CIC-APT-IIoT-2024 dataset, which contains advanced persistent threats (APT), the overall accuracy reaches 99.977%, with normal traffic detection performing exceptionally well at 99.992% accuracy. Notably, several attack categories, including “Credential Access”, “Command and Control”, “Discovery”, and “Lateral Movement”, achieve 100% accuracy, indicating that all positive instances were correctly classified without any false negatives. The precision and recall values for most attack types are also near or at 100%, ensuring a balanced detection of both attack and normal traffic. The lowest precision value is observed in “Cleanup” (98.044%), which suggests a slight tendency for false positives in this category. However, the F1-scores consistently exceed 99%, reflecting

the robustness of the model in accurately detecting all threats. Figure 2 presents the multiclass confusion matrix, further illustrating the model’s classification performance.

For the WUSTL-IIoT-2021 dataset, the approach maintains high detection accuracy (99.980%), demonstrating strong generalization capabilities across different IIoT environments. The model successfully identifies normal traffic with 99.987% accuracy while also excelling in detecting complex cyber threats. For example, the “Command Injection” attack achieves an impressive precision of 99.313% and recall of 99.318%, resulting in an F1-score of 99.331%. Similarly, “DoS” attacks are effectively detected with 99.988% accuracy, ensuring minimal misclassifications. The “Backdoor” attack, while still achieving a high F1-score of 98.315%, shows a slightly lower precision (96.687%), indicating some false positives in this category. Figure 3 presents the multiclass confusion matrix, providing further insight into classification effectiveness.

Lastly, in the WUSTL-IIoT-2018 dataset, the model continues to deliver exceptional results in a binary classification setting. Both normal traffic and attack categories achieve a near-perfect accuracy of 99.984%. The recall for attacks reaches 100%, meaning all attack instances were correctly classified with no false negatives, while the precision remains high at 99.958%, resulting

in an overall F1-score of 99.979%. This indicates that the model not only detects all attacks but also maintains an extremely low false positive rate, which is critical for real-world IIoT. Figure 4 presents the binary confusion matrix, highlighting the effectiveness of the proposed approach in distinguishing between normal and attack traffic. The results presented in Table III presents a comparative analysis of our proposed approach against state-of-the-art classifiers from existing studies.

For the CIC-APT-IIoT-2024 dataset, which contains sophisticated advanced persistent threats (APT) scenarios, our proposed approach clearly outperforms existing solutions, achieving an overall accuracy of 99.9765%. This result significantly surpasses the accuracy reported by existing studies, such as the ensemble model combining Random Forest and XGBoost from [15] (accuracy: 98.00%) and the PCA-based enhanced Deep Neural Network proposed in [16] (accuracy: 95.20%). Moreover, our model yields exceptionally high precision, recall, and F1-scores (all approximately 99.98%), demonstrating robust and reliable performance in precisely distinguishing normal traffic from diverse sophisticated cyber-attacks.

For the WUSTL-IIoT-2021 dataset, our model again showcases remarkable performance, achieving an accuracy of 99.9733%. Compared to classifiers such as Naïve Bayes [17] (accuracy: 97.95%) and CNN [18] (accuracy: 99.94%), our proposed method achieves

Fig. 3. Confusion Matrix of Multiclass Classification on WUSTL-IIoT-2021 Dataset

Fig. 4. Confusion Matrix of Binary Classification on WUSTL-IIoT-2018 Dataset

Fig. 2. Confusion Matrix of Multiclass Classification on CIC-APT-IIoT-2024 Dataset

better balance between precision and recall (both at approximately 99.97%), resulting in an impressive F1-score of 99.9733%. Notably, our IDS demonstrates superior performance in terms of recall, minimizing false negatives across challenging attack categories like "Backdoor" and "Command Injection." Although the SVM+LDA method [19] reported a nominal accuracy of 100%, it has lower recall and F1-score values, highlighting that our model offers a more balanced and reliable detection of intrusions, especially in real-world scenarios characterized by class imbalance.

The evaluation on the WUSTL-IIoT-2018 dataset confirms the superior performance of our proposed IDS with a remarkable overall accuracy of 99.9841%. This result clearly outperforms other recent approaches like LDA [22] (accuracy: 93.11%), Deep Q-Learning [21] (accuracy: 99.36%), RNN [23] (accuracy: 99.09%), and Transformer Neural Network [24] (accuracy: 98.54%). Importantly, our model achieves perfect recall (100%) on attack detection, meaning it effectively identifies every instance of intrusion attempts without false neg-

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF PROPOSED APPROACH USING CIC-APT-IIoT-2024, WUSTL-IIoT-2021, WUSTL-IIoT-2018 DATASETS

Dataset	Labels	TP	TN	FP	FN	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
CIC-APT-IIoT 2024	Normal	99971	2405	1	23	99.977	99.999	99.977	99.988
	Cleanup	401	101991	8	0	99.992	98.044	100.00	99.012
	Collection	513	101878	8	1	99.991	98.464	99.805	99.130
	Command & Control	180	102219	1	0	99.999	99.448	100.00	99.723
	Credential Access	183	102217	0	0	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Discovery	329	102070	1	0	99.999	99.697	100.00	99.848
	Exfiltration	279	102120	1	0	99.999	99.643	100.00	99.821
	Lateral Movement	219	102180	1	0	99.999	99.545	100.00	99.772
Persistence	301	102096	3	0	99.997	99.013	100.00	99.504	
WUSTL-IIOT 2021	Normal	99914	23661	10	15	99.980	99.990	99.985	99.987
	Backdoor	321	123268	11	0	99.991	96.687	100.00	98.315
	Command Injection	289	123307	2	2	99.997	99.313	99.313	99.313
	DoS	20016	103566	5	13	99.985	99.975	99.935	99.955
	Reconnaissance	3027	120565	5	3	99.994	99.835	99.901	99.868
WUSTL-IIoT 2018	Normal	7863	4727	0	2	99.984	100.00	99.975	99.987
	Attack	4727	7863	2	0	99.984	99.958	100.00	99.979

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF PROPOSED APPROACH WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART CLASSIFIERS USING CIC-APT-IIoT-2024, WUSTL-IIoT-2021, WUSTL-IIoT-2018 DATASETS

Dataset	Study	Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
CIC-APT-IIoT-2024	Proposed	BERT and MLP	99.9765	99.9768	99.9765	99.9766
	[15]	Ensemble Model (RF and XGBoost)	98.00	99.00	95.00	96.00
	[16]	PCA-based Enhanced DNN	95.20	93.10	92.70	92.60
WUSTL-IIOT-2021	Proposed	BERT and MLP	99.9733	99.9735	99.9733	99.9733
	[17]	Naïve Bayes	97.95	89.09	98.87	93.31
	[18]	CNN	99.94	94.74	92.29	93.41
	[19]	SVM+LDA	100	98.48	92.54	94.84
	[20]	Autoencoders	99.95	99.71	99.72	96.31
	[21]	Deep Q-Learning	98.62	99.23	98.62	99.23
WUSTL-IIoT-2018	Proposed	BERT and MLP	99.9841	99.9577	100.00	99.9788
	[22]	LDA	93.11	94.00	93.00	93.00
	[21]	Deep Q-Learning	99.36	99.40	99.38	99.36
	[23]	RNN	99.09	97.12	96.45	95.05
	[24]	Transformer Neural Network	98.54	98.70	98.42	98.61

atives. The very high precision (99.9577%) and F1-score (99.9788%) underscore the model's exceptional capability in minimizing false positives, making it highly practical for securing critical industrial networks. Overall, the comprehensive performance analysis presented demonstrates the effectiveness, reliability, and robustness of our BERT and MLP-based IDS. These outstanding results indicate that our proposed approach significantly surpasses other state-of-the-art methods across all considered metrics, emphasizing its practical applicability and superiority in enhancing cybersecurity resilience in real-world industrial IoT.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we presented a deep learning-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) specifically tailored to secure Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) environments. Our approach utilizes Google BERT for advanced contextual feature extraction combined with an MLP classifier, significantly enhancing the detection of sophisticated cyber threats in complex IIoT network scenarios. The model's performance was thoroughly evaluated using three benchmark datasets (CIC-APT-IIoT-2024, WUSTL-IIoT-2021, and WUSTL-IIoT-2018), demonstrating superior accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score compared to recent state-of-the-

art methodologies. The results confirmed that our approach effectively addresses class imbalance through SMOTE and consistently identifies various IIoT-specific attacks. Future research directions include evaluating the model's generalizability with additional diverse IIoT datasets and further optimization of computational efficiency to enable real-time deployments in operational industrial networks.

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